

TEXT-BASED VOCABULARY INSTRUCTION AS A LEARNING TOOL FOR EFL FRESHMEN'S READING COMPREHENSION

Nhung Hong Thi Pham¹,

Huan Buu Nguyen²

¹Mekong University, Vietnam

²Can Tho University, Vietnam

Abstract

This paper reports a study which examines how text-based vocabulary instruction influences English as a foreign language (EFL) freshmen's reading comprehension and explore their perceptions on this type of instruction in reading comprehension. It was a quasi- experimental study with control and experimental groups including eighty freshmen at a university. The quantitative data from reading tests for pre-test and post-test were used to examine students' reading comprehension over nine weeks. The qualitative analysis used semi-structured interviews to examine students' perceptions towards text-based vocabulary instruction in reading comprehension. The findings reveal that text-based vocabulary instruction influenced positively students' reading achievement after the experiment and that they had positive perceptions towards this type of instruction in their reading lessons.

Keywords: perceptions, reading comprehension, text-based, vocabulary instruction

1. Introduction

It is widely held that vocabulary plays an essential role in teaching and learning a foreign or second language as it is not a goal in itself; rather, it enables learners to improve four language skills: listening, speaking, reading and writing (e.g., [N. T. Le & Nguyen, 2012](#); [Nation, 2001](#); [Richards, Gallo, & Renandya, 2001](#); [Schmitt, 2008](#)). It is therefore vocabulary and reading are intertwined in ways that vocabulary gains speed up the process of comprehending a particular text and that reading allows learners to build up their language proficiency, thereby influencing how learners approach and digest information in response to educational, professional, and occupational contexts.

This recognition is advocated by the Vietnamese government's assertion of the need for the quality of teaching and learning foreign languages through the national foreign languages 2020 project ([Ministry of Education and Training, 2008](#)). In particular, it is expected that by 2020, the Vietnamese students are able to use foreign languages confidently in communication, studies or their work in a competitive world. However, in the context of English language learning at universities in Vietnam, especially in the Mekong Delta, it was observed that English as a foreign language (EFL) students found it difficult to learn text-based vocabulary because they generally learn new words relying on the teacher's support or guide in class ([T. T. H. Nguyen & Khuat, 2003](#)). Besides, in the context of teaching reading at Vietnam, students had passive attitudes towards learning vocabulary because teaching at universities is largely based on traditional lecturing ([T. K. Le & Nguyen, 2017](#); [B. H. Nguyen, 2013](#)). Moreover, the traditional vocabulary instruction in use, to some extent, was not viewed as an effective way to help students to communicate in English ([N. T. Le & Nguyen, 2012](#)). This passive learning may be due to how students learn new words influenced by mother-tongue translation, which slows down their reading comprehension and or even makes them misunderstand reading contents. Thus, examining these challenges students encountered in learning text-based vocabulary is necessary. This paper is therefore aimed at exploring the impact of text-based vocabulary instruction on students' reading comprehension and their perceptions of this type of instruction in reading classes.

The following section reviews the literature on four concepts: vocabulary, vocabulary instruction, text-based approach, and reading comprehension.

2. Vocabulary

There are several definitions of vocabulary in the literature ([McShane, 2005](#); [Oxford, 1990](#); [Papadopoulou, 2007](#)). McShane (2005) defines vocabulary as knowledge of word and its meanings. This implies that vocabulary plays an indispensable part in learning and understanding a particular text. According to Papadopoulou (2007), vocabulary is defined as knowledge of words and the ability to use these words in generating and understanding sentence meanings. In this way, vocabulary is particularly associated with words learners know and use to comprehend them in a variety of contexts productively. These conceptualizations of vocabulary address the role it plays in students' reading learning process while communicating and using language.

2.1 Vocabulary instruction

Vocabulary instruction has come to the forefront of the discussion of reading and comprehension ([Pearson, Hiebert, & Kamil, 2007](#)). For the study reported in this paper, three ways to teach vocabulary include guessing meaning from the context, making lexical inferences and using synonyms in reading teaching.

A. Guessing the meaning from context

Guessing the meaning of words from context is widely known as an effective tool to help students comprehend reading texts. Thus, they are required to focus on context clues to guess the meanings of unfamiliar or new words in written text passages ([Laufer & Bensusan, 1982](#)). It is necessary to help students to understand the surrounding words within the same sentence can provide the useful hints about the meaning of a word or its structure. The richness of information in a given context enables a reader to guess an unknown word successfully ([Nation & Coady, 1988](#)). Moreover, Nation ([2001](#)) argues that learning vocabulary by guessing from context is the most important of all sources of vocabulary learning. He also confirms guessing the meaning of words from context, can be learned deductively, suitable for young learners, or inductively appropriate for teaching other learners. Thus, it is the role of the teacher who provides students with different techniques to understand how to examine the word meanings they encounter by giving a definition, using synonyms, antonyms or discussion of a new word ([Tankersley, 2008](#)).

B. Synonyms

A synonym is a way to help learners understand more about the meaning of a word as well as enhance their amount of vocabulary. Nation ([2001](#)) asserts that learning a synonym for a word already known may be easier than learning a non-synonym. A synonym may be used to help the student to understand the different shades of meaning, if the synonym is better known than the word being taught ([Mothe, 2000](#)). According to Lehr, Osborn and Hiebert ([2004](#)), connecting important words to synonyms before students read a given text can be an efficient and minimally disruptive way to help them get the most from reading. The use of synonyms can be an effective way for learners to learn new words by stressing that learning synonyms of known words allow learners to gain considerable vocabulary knowledge in a shorter period of time in comparison to that of non-synonyms ([Webb, 2007](#)). It is for this reason teachers should provide opportunities for students to practice new words and their synonyms in the reading text.

C. Lexical inferences

Lexical inference is a useful way in students' reading. Chikalanga ([1992](#)) presents the taxonomy of inference in reading, which was divided into three basic categories: lexical,

propositional, and pragmatic or scriptal inferences. Among them, lexical inferences as *"inferring the referents of pronominals and meanings of ambiguous and unfamiliar lexical items through contextual clues"* ([Chikalanga, 1992, p. 704](#)). Clearly, lexical inferences are defined as inferences that readers make to identify the referents of pronominals and disambiguate unknown lexical terms from the context in which they occur ([Chikalanga, 1993](#)). For example, in order to understand what the word "he" is referring to in text, the reader must combine information in that sentence with information in a previous sentence that referred to as a male. Furthermore, Read ([2000](#)) summarizes the role of lexical inference as *"a desirable strategy because it involves deeper processing that is likely to contribute to better comprehension of the text as a whole and may result in some learning of the lexical item that would not otherwise occur"* (p. 53). Pronoun reference is viewed as a critical factor in lexical inference ([Nation, 2001](#)). Hence, in the current study, the lexical inference is considered as checking the students' referents in their reading tests.

2.2 Text-based approach

A. Text

A text is defined in several ways in the literature by different researchers ([Gracia, 1996](#); [Guzzetti, 2002](#); [Nuttall, 1996, 2005](#)). Nuttall ([1996](#)) claims that a text is accessible to the mind of another person who reads or hears it, and who may then decode the message it contains. Moreover, a text is more likely to be seen as something that consists of well-formed sentences in sequence ([Courter, 2014](#)). Guzzetti (2002) argues that a text is a coherent written message that can take the form of a range of narrative and expository materials, such as a page in a novel, a newspaper or magazine article, a book or short story, the print on a computer, or a chapter in a textbook. Text is mentioned as a collection of pieces of information written in order to interpret messages to readers. In the current study, a text is defined as a written message that has well-structured sentences to convey meaning to the readers.

B. Text-based approach

Text-based approach is popular for learners when they acquire vocabulary through reading texts. Texts as linguistic objects are used for language work, specifically grammar or vocabulary ([Johns & Davies, 1983](#)). Besides, Nagy ([1988](#)) asserts that a teacher might write one or two sentences on the board containing the word to be learned, and ask students to figure out what the word means. As language occurs in form of text rather than isolated words and sentences ([Thornbury, 2005](#)), when learning a language through texts, learners can enrich word information such as word meaning, lexical chain and word association.

The functions of text in teaching vocabulary are considered by some researchers. Nuttall (1996) contends that to get students interested in reading texts is more critical than either the linguistic level of the text or its exploitability. Johns and Davies (1983) argue that when using texts in learning and teaching vocabulary, a text can be described as a linguistic object, a vehicle for information and a stimulus for production. They also point out that a text as a stimulus for production means using a text as a springboard for another task – usually a reading or writing task. Tomlinson (2005) claims that an interesting text to read is what teachers or learners want to get from the book. Furthermore, texts are accessible for reading, for action, and for information at all age levels and proficiency levels (Mickan, 2011; Mickan & Lopez, 2017). Undoubtedly, text is a vehicle for learners to develop their vocabulary. Therefore, teachers are responsible for choosing pertinent text to students learning so as to motivate them to learn as well as develop new words from these texts.

C. Types of text

Narrative and expository texts are two typical text types that influence readers' understanding or comprehending a given text (Alderson, 2000; Landers, 2010; Saadatnia, Ketabi, & Tavakoli, 2017). According to Alderson (2000), narrative and expository texts are found to be most different from each other as having different functions in relation to reading comprehension. These include content, word frequency, causality, and structure (Saadatnia et al., 2017). While narrative text mainly focuses on one text structure or topics of interest, expository text contains more complex content and high level vocabulary that requires readers to make explicit ideas, explore or interpret the information in greater depth through describing, comparing, contrasting, and problem solving (Hanson & Padua, 2011; Smith, 2003). Glende (2013) further claims that expository texts, or informational texts, contain factual information and more unfamiliar vocabulary and concepts. Thus, learners may find the content of narrative texts more familiar than expository texts as exposition includes technical words that may or may not be defined in the text (Gardner, 2004).

2.3 Reading comprehension

There are several definitions of reading comprehension in the literature. Reading comprehension is an interactive process that takes place between a reader and a text (Nuttall, 1996, 2005; Rumelhart, 1994). Reading comprehension is *“the process of simultaneously extracting and constructing meaning through interaction and involvement with written language”* (Snow, 2002, p. 11). In the same vein, Pang and his colleagues (2003) describe reading comprehension as an active process that a reader constructs meaning from a text. Furthermore, Grabe (2009) contends that reading is a combination of

complex processes that are “*rapid, efficient, interactive, strategic, flexible, evaluative, purposeful, comprehending, learning, and linguistic*” (p. 14). To put it simply, reading is an active and dynamic process of comprehending a given text that requires learners to use various strategies during reading ([B. H. Nguyen & Nguyen, 2017](#)). In this paper, reading comprehension refers to an interactive process of understanding of a subject specific text through which learners use their knowledge to decode, interpret its printed messages and make sense of word meanings within the text.

A. The vocabulary-reading relationship

It is widely held that vocabulary and reading comprehension are intertwined in language and teaching reading by several researchers ([Eskey, 2005](#); [Freebody & Anderson, 1983](#); [Grabe, 1991, 2009](#); [Gungor & Yayli, 2016](#); [Stanovich, 1986](#); [Sternberg, 1987](#)). Gungor and Yayli ([2016](#)) assert that a learner's ability to comprehend a text mainly depends on vocabulary knowledge. In addition, reading can broaden learners' language competence by providing automaticity of recognizing and decoding words and written symbols of a printed message ([Grabe, 2009](#)). The relative difficulty of the text is a function of the percentage of unknown vocabulary words ([Carver, 1994](#)). Or in other words, a learner's effective reading of a text is proportion to the amount of vocabulary gains ([Schmitt, 2000, 2008, 2010](#)). Moreover, the heart of language comprehension and use is the lexicon ([Hunt & Beglar, 2005](#)). Thus, vocabulary and reading are seen as two major language components that help develop learners' language ability and skills needed in their learning process. To add to the knowledge of text-based vocabulary instruction and reading comprehension, this paper specifically focuses on the impact of text-based vocabulary instruction on reading comprehension of non-English majored students. In doing so, it responds to the following research questions:

- What is the impact of text-based vocabulary instruction on EFL freshmen's reading comprehension?
- What are EFL freshmen's perceptions towards text-based vocabulary instruction that influences their reading comprehension?

3. Methodology

Mixed methods research was used to answer two research questions in this study. According to Creswell ([2014](#)), mixed methods research is an approach to inquiry that combines both qualitative and quantitative forms of research. This type of research allows for more insights into the research problem under investigation than does the use of either form alone ([Fraenkel, Wallen, & Hyun, 2012](#)). The quantitative approach

was implemented to explore the impact of text-based vocabulary instruction on EFL freshmen's reading comprehension. The qualitative approach was applied to investigate participants' perceptions on text-based vocabulary instruction that influences their reading comprehension.

The participants in this study include eighty non-English major freshmen from a Vietnamese university in the Mekong Delta. Their age ranges between 18 and 20. They have studied Basic English Two, a requirement for non-English major students in the second semester of the academic year 2016-1017. The selection for choosing participants in this study was based on convenience sampling technique ([Fraenkel et al., 2012](#)). This aims at selecting students who were available and accessible at the university and it allows for easy administering the data collection procedures. The participants from two classes were assigned into two groups: control and experimental. There were forty students in the control group (30 females and 10 males) and forty in the experimental group (26 females and 14 males). Before the study, the participants' proficiency English language level was similar in both groups, evidenced by the results of the scores of their final English reading exams in the previous semester.

The quantitative data were used to compare EFL freshmen's progress from control and experimental groups. Furthermore, it was applied to measure the extent to which text-based vocabulary instruction influences freshmen's reading comprehension. During nine weeks, all learners from control and experimental groups were exposed to the same reading tasks in the books. After administering the pre-test for two groups, students from the experimental group received text-based vocabulary instruction from the teacher whereas the control group did not receive. At the end of the experiment in nine weeks, a post-test measure was administered to both groups. After administering the post-test, interviews were conducted with six participants from the experimental group in order to investigate their perceptions on text-based vocabulary instruction that may influence their reading comprehension.

The pre-test and post-test were selected from New Headway English course-Elementary tests ([Maris, 2001](#)). Their contents have familiar topics to students' learning including food, health, education, and sports. The pretest and posttest were similar in format, instruction, length, the level of difficulty and allotted time but the specific reading topics between the two tests were different.

Each test had two reading texts and each reading text was a combination of two parts. Part One was designed with a cloze test consisting six gaps whereas part two was designed four multiple-choice questions. In Part Two, it was designed with four multiple choice questions, as indicated by Nuttall ([1996](#)), as a common device for testing text comprehension. Two questions were designed in terms of recognizing referents for

particular pronouns. She further claims that inference questions may require the reader to put together pieces of information in multiple parts of the text. The next two questions were asked about the synonyms of a noun and an adjective basing on the text (see Appendix A).

3.1 Piloting the pre-test and post-test

Firstly, the test format, instructions, and contents of the pre-test and post-test were read and checked by the supervisor. Next, the pre-test and post-test were piloted to ensure the reliability of this instrument. 33 non-English major students, who have the similar background to the participants of the research, were chosen to participate in the pilot tests. The Cronbach's alpha for the pretest was .74 and that of the posttest was .76, indicating the reliability of the tests used to collect the data for the study.

Semi-structured interviews were conducted to explore students' perceptions towards text-based vocabulary instruction that influences their reading comprehension. This type of interview is seen as less rigid than other types of interviews ([Mackey & Gass, 2005](#)) because it allowed for the interviewer to have more freedom to get insights into respondents' views. Such investigative tool is known as a useful way to complement the other, namely tests.

The interviews consisted of five open questions that were designed by the researcher. The interview questions were checked for consistency and content by the supervisor. The questions' contents were asked about students' opinion about the use of text-based vocabulary instruction in reading comprehension class, the benefits and challenges of text-based vocabulary instruction in their reading comprehension, and their application of text-based vocabulary instruction in their reading comprehension (see Appendix B).

Teaching materials used in this study were New Headway Elementary – Student's Book and New Headway Pre-intermediate–Student's Book ([Soars & Soars, 2000](#)). In this course, six units from units 9 to 14 of the New Headway Elementary – Student's Book and two units 1 and 2 of the New Headway Pre-intermediate – Student's Book were taught. Each unit has a reading text except unit 11. The reading texts of an average of 300 words describing topics of daily lives including food, sport, music, culture, travelling, and stories.

The quantitative data collected from the pre-test and post-test was statistically analyzed using the computer software Statistics Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. The qualitative data from the interviews were hand-coded using interview protocols in which the topics or themes emerged.

4. Findings

4.1 Students' reading comprehension

a) Before the experiment

The result of the *Independent Samples t-Test* on the pre-test showed that the mean score of students' reading in the control group ($M = .62$, $SD = .12$) was similar to that of the experimental group ($M = .63$, $SD = .18$). Thus, both groups did not differ significantly ($t = -.25$, $df = 78$, $p = .80$) in their reading comprehension. It could be concluded that before the study, students' level of reading comprehension of the two groups was not significantly different, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Independent Samples t-Test of the two groups on pre-test

Test	Condition	N	t	df	Mean	Sig. (2-tailed)	MD	SD
Pre-test	Control	40	-.25	78	.62	.80	-.01	.12
	Experimental	40			.63			.18

b) After the experiment

The result of the *Independent Samples t-Test* on the post-test showed that the mean score of students' reading comprehension in the experimental group ($M = .72$, $SD = .13$) was higher than that of the control group ($M = .65$, $SD = .12$). The students' reading comprehension post-test scores between two groups was significantly different ($t = -2.52$, $df = 78$, $p = .01$). It could be seen that students' reading comprehension in the experimental group was higher than that of the control group after the study. The results also revealed that the students who received text-based vocabulary instruction obtained more than the students who did not get text-based vocabulary instruction.

Table 2: Independent Samples t-test of two groups on post-test

Test	Condition	N	t	df	Mean	Sig. (2-tailed)	MD	SD
Post-test	Control	40	-2.52	78	.65	.01	-.01	.12
	Experimental	40			.72			.13

These above results have shown that the students' reading comprehension of the control group and experimental group were at the same level before the study. After the study, the students' level of reading in the experimental group outweighed that of the control group. However, the students' level of reading in the control group did not change after the study. Figure 1 displays students' reading achievement of both groups.

Figure 1: Students' reading comprehension between and within the two groups

4.2 Students' perceptions about text-based vocabulary instruction

Analyses from the interview data revealed that six participating students understood the meaning of text-based vocabulary instruction and perceived this type of instruction as positive while learning reading. For example, Thuy stated,

"At the beginning of the reading lesson, when the teacher provides me with vocabulary, and asks me to look at the context of a text, I understand these words surrounding it are related, and then I can guess the meaning of that vocabulary (Thuy, from high test scores)."

Tuyen suggests that text-based vocabulary instruction was useful as it allowed her to relate what she has known to figure out the meaning of unknown words when reading a new text. She shared her views:

"I think that text-based technique can help me think of what the word means. By doing this way I can remember that new word longer instead of translating word by word as I used to (Tuyen, from average scores)."

From Tuyen's comment, it appears that she not only came to know a new way of learning to retain words but also moved herself beyond the traditional way of learning vocabulary.

When asked regarding how students felt at the end of the study, all interviewed students reported that this new way of learning vocabulary was interesting. For instance, Nga (low score student) said,

"After studying how to guess meanings of new words from the context, I found this type of instruction interesting. Well, certainly there are some words I did not know or understand in the lessons until being told or explained by the teacher (Nga, from low scores)."

Furthermore, all interviewees asserted that this instruction could enrich their vocabulary knowledge through the use of synonyms or antonyms. For instance, Hang indicated,

"I can learn more new vocabulary from the synonyms or antonyms guided by the teacher. Since then, I use such clues to understand the lesson quickly. Importantly, it motivates me to do further exercise better. (Hang, from high scores)."

However, when asked what difficulties participating students had to encounter when learning reading comprehension with text-based vocabulary instruction; only one student revealed that translation could slow down their reading process or even lead to misunderstanding of word meanings in a reading passage. Kieu said,

"There are so many new words even a phrase in a paragraph. At that time, I had to translate. I break the sentences into parts then translate words in isolation. Thus, such translation is a waste of time and sometimes can lead me to wrong meanings (Kieu, from average scores)."

Regarding the application of text-based technique in reading, students reported that they could apply this new learning tool. Han shared her practice:

"Before every lesson, I usually take a quick look or preview the reading text to see if words are difficult or connected with others. I think I will learn more vocabulary as such gains help me understand the word meanings and structures or formation for effective reading (Han, from average scores)."

This quote suggests that Han perceived the importance of previewing the text and structural elements and consequently through her background knowledge of word parts this could help her extend comprehension of a given text.

Overall, the findings from the interview data reveal that students had the positive attitudes towards the implementation of the text-based vocabulary instruction in their reading classes. Although there were some difficulties reported by one student, students recognized the usefulness of such type of instruction as it influenced how students learned to read.

5. Discussion

The findings indicate that the students in the experimental group had significant improvement in their reading comprehension while students in the control group did not improve after the study. It could be concluded that teaching text-based vocabulary improved EFL freshmen's reading comprehension. Such improvement supports a study by Chou (2011), Anjomshoa and Zamanian (2014), and Theldja (2015) who confirmed that students provided with vocabulary lists could enhance their reading comprehension.

Specific techniques of text-based vocabulary instruction identified as guessing the meaning from context and synonyms as well as inferring word meaning through previewing were reported in this study. This finding confirms the importance of guessing the meaning from context in learning, as advocated by Nation (2001) and the benefit of synonyms in reading, as confirmed by Lehr and her colleagues (2004) who maintained that synonyms are an effective way that allows students to get across the reading passages. Students' lexical inference reflects its strong interplay with their reading comprehension when they were exposed to connect learning new texts to prior knowledge and experiences (Read, 2000; Tankersley, 2008). Understanding the role of these techniques in contributing to increased comprehension of a text suggests that teachers should move their students forward new ways of learning and encourage them to endeavor a variety of texts suitable and useful for their specific and future needs, academically and professionally.

The findings of the impact of text-based vocabulary instruction on EFL students' reading comprehension stress the significant function of texts- narrative and expository types in students' learning vocabulary and reading comprehension. These text types have motivated students' learning through reading tests. This concurs with the literature that indicates the benefits of using texts to motivate students to learn more

vocabulary and develop their reading learning ([Mickan, 2011](#); [Mickan & Lopez, 2017](#); [Tomlinson, 2005](#)).

The findings from the interview reveal that students recognized the relationship of vocabulary knowledge and reading comprehension as evidenced by how they perceived the usefulness of vocabulary gains that extend their comprehension. This supports the claims from Schmitt ([2000](#)), Hunt and Beglar ([2005](#)) and Grabe ([2009](#)) who contended that reading is the most important language skill that aids learners in improving their vocabulary knowledge and acquisition.

Students' positive perceptions towards the implementation of the teaching text-based vocabulary could be shown through students' learning progress in their reading performance. This kind of implementation helped them enhance and retain vocabulary, figure out word meanings from the text as well as involve them to do further reading exercises. It was observed that participating students found this text-based instruction a new learning way that moved them forward in reading practices. This finding confirms the claim of studies by Marzano ([2004](#)), McMillen ([2009](#)), and Johnson and Johnson ([2012](#)) who highlighted that vocabulary instruction was a vital component to develop students' reading performance.

6. Conclusions

The findings from this present study present the value of text-based vocabulary instruction on freshmen's reading comprehension and their positive perceptions towards this type of instruction. In particular, how to teach reading lessons through text-based vocabulary strategies is needed to take into account. Awareness of students' perceptions towards text-based vocabulary instruction may provide teachers with opportunities to improve their teaching practices and student learning reading in similar contexts. It is recommended that teachers need to provide students with a large amount of reading texts related to their real-life activities and interests. In doing so, students will see how reading and vocabulary knowledge benefit their reading learning process. Moreover, an exciting classroom atmosphere with the most favorable learning environment is also created in reading classes so that learners can read and discuss freely with their peers in the classroom. Students, in the reading process, need to be engaged in reading activities including working in pairs or groups to figure out meanings of words, sentences and texts, share ideas and opinions about, critique or reflect on a particular text message. It is recommended that teachers are encouraged to attend professional development workshops and training courses in reading research so that they will make their own teaching contexts more effective by engaging their

students in knowing how to learn better and explore other word learning and reading strategies for their own disciplines.

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APPENDIX A

Reading Test (Sample)

Reading text 1

Part 1: Complete the text. Choose the correct word from the box.

population	famous	hear
historic	visit	traffic

London has a (1)..... of about 7,000,000. **It** lies on the River Thames, where the Romans landed nearly 2,000 years ago. From about 1800 until World War Two, London was the biggest city in the world, but now there are many cities which are much bigger. London is (2).....for many things. Tourists come from all over the world to visit its (3).....buildings, such as Buckingham **Palace**, and the Houses of Parliament, where you can see and (4)..... the famous clock, Big Ben. **They** also come to (5)..... its theatres, its museums, and its many shops, such as Harrods, where you can buy anything. Any of course, they want to ride on the big wheel next to the river! Like many big cities, London has problems with (6)..... and pollution. Over 1,000,000 people a day use the London Underground, but there are still too many cars on the streets. The air isn't **clean**, but it is cleaner than it was 100 years ago.

Part 2: Read the text above and choose the correct letter A, B, C or D.

7. The word 'it' in line 1 refers to
A. River B. London C. population D. 7,000,000
8. The word '**they**' in line 6 refers to
A. tourists B. things C. Houses D. shops
9. The word '**clean**' in line 10 is closest in meaning to
A. tidy B. pure C. simple D. bright
10. The word '**palace**' in line 5 is closest in meaning to
A. place B. home of Queen C. home of King D. House of Parliament

APPENDIX B

Interview Questions

1. Can you tell me what text-based vocabulary instruction is?
2. What do you think about the use of text-based vocabulary instruction in reading comprehension classes?
3. What are the benefits of text-based vocabulary instruction in your reading comprehension classes?
4. What are the challenges of text-based vocabulary instruction in your reading comprehension classes?
5. In order to learn better, what do you do to apply text-based vocabulary instruction in your reading comprehension classes?

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